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Psychological Realism versus Magical Realism: A Critical Study of Toni

Morrison's *Beloved* (1987)

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Abstract:

Toni Morrison's much-acclaimed fictional work, *Beloved* (1987) is studied much both for the presentation of the psychological realism of the past inhuman slavery and its revelation in the experimental magical realism. Magical realism was made popular by Gabriel Garcia Marquez and Salman Rushdie, who used it extensively in the novels, *One Hundred Years of Solitude* (1967) and *Midnight Children* (1981) respectively. Morrison seems to be very much influenced by this Latin American genre of novel writing, since her Pulitzer-Prize winning novel, *Beloved* has followed the traditional blending of realism and fantasy in the story as a cure for national amnesia, regarding the shameful history of African-American slavery. The two dominant characters in this novel are Sethe, the black slave woman whose mind is haunted by her horrible deed of infanticide, and her resurrected daughter, Beloved, who is killed by her twenty years ago.

The plot of the novel is non-linear; the thoughts, emotions and complexities of human

psychology are expressed by a series of flashbacks, interior monologues in fragmented speeches and the fluctuations of mind by stream-of-consciousness. One of the primary themes of the psychological novel is the burden of the haunting past memories which makes the present crippled without any hope for future. This research-paper intends to highlight the intertwining between psychological realism and magical realism that makes this novel both realistic and fabulous.

Keywords: Psychological Realism, Magical Realism, Slavery, Stream-of-Consciousness, Non-Linear.

Introduction:

By the end of the 18th century and in the beginning of the 19th century, psychological probe in literature has become very much in fashion because the philosophers and writers start believe that the inner life of a person controls his/her outer life. Moreover, the two epoch-making books of Sigmund Freud, *The Interpretation of Dreams* (1899) and *The Psychopathology of Everyday Life* (1904) had established a very close relationship between the literature, dealing with human predicament or delusions on the one hand and the complexities of human psychology on the other. S.T. Coleridge is hailed as the first modern poet-critic by Eliot and Richards because it was Coleridge who made literature interdisciplinary by connecting it to psychology. In his most-celebrated narrative poem, *The Rime of the Ancient Mariner* (1798), Coleridge reveals the psychological realism of the ancient Mariner who tries to teach every sensitive person to love God by loving and caring for all creatures, whether big or small, made by God. The narrative technique, used by Coleridge, works like a kind of magical realism because the Wedding Guest, an ordinary person with his physical presence, gets very much involved in and captivated by the

past history of crime and punishment narrated to him by such a supernatural being, the Ancient Mariner. The other two notable examples of psychological realism, expressed in the moulding of magical realism, are Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Crime and Punishment* (1866) and Henry James' *The Bostonians* (1886) which deal with inner complex lives of the ruminating protagonists. Psychological realism explores the inner man/person and his/her persistent abnormal behavior and thought which generally remain incurable. The complexities of the inner man are expressed in a highly poetic language including motifs and symbols, which creates a kind of magical ambience in the plot of the artistic creation. Psychological realism remains rooted in the actual time of the mental problem or trauma which becomes the mental time of the protagonist, annihilating the psychological time and problem from its present and future. The plot of the novel or narrative poem, dealing with the psychological realism, is never linear or chronological in narration; instead, it is always circular or non-linear in nature. The thoughts, emotions and complexities of human psychology are expressed by a series of flashbacks, interior monologues in fragmented speeches and the fluctuations of mind by stream-of-consciousness. One of the primary themes of the psychological novels is the burden of the haunting past memories that makes the present crippled without any hope for future. This problem of the unbearable past life may involve not only the present generation, but also the preceding and the succeeding generations. Toni Morrison's much-acclaimed fictional work, *Beloved* (1987) is studied much both for the presentation of the psychological realism of the past inhuman slavery and its revelation in the experimental magical realism. Magical realism was made popular by Gabriel Garcia Marquez and Salman Rushdie, who had used it extensively in their novels, *One Hundred Years of Solitude* (1967) and *Midnight Children* (1981) respectively. Morrison seems to be very much influenced by this Latin American genre of novel writing, since her Pulitzer Prize winning

novel, *Beloved* has followed this traditional blending of realism and fantasy in the story as a cure for national amnesia, regarding the shameful history of African-American Slavery. The story of *Beloved* is based upon the psychological turmoil and dilemma of a real African-American enslaved-woman, Margaret Garner, who tried to escape from the degrading slavery through her flight from Kentucky to the free state of Ohio. Unfortunately, She and her children had been pursued by the slave-owners under the Fugitive Slave Act of 1850; When Margaret and her children were about to be recaptured, she became so much panic-hysterical that she virtually killed her two-year-old daughter. Morrison, representing the collective consciousness of Past Transatlantic slave trade, has recreated this traumatic incident into the novel, *Beloved*, with the dedication, 'Sixty Million and more' which has both historical and cultural connotations. This research-paper intends to highlight the intertwining between psychological realism and magical realism that makes the novel both realistic and fabulous.

Exposition:

In *Beloved*, the two dominant characters who matter much are, Sethe, the black enslaved woman whose mind is haunted by her own horrible deed of infanticide, and her resurrected daughter, Beloved, who is killed by her twenty years ago. As Morrison herself accepts: 'The historical Margaret Garner is fascinating, but, to a novelist, confining. Too little imaginative space there for my purposes. So I would invent her thoughts, plumb them for a subtext that was historically true in essence, but not strictly factual in order to relate her history to contemporary issues about freedom, responsibility, and women's place' (Morrison: Foreword/2005: XI). The story begins with the description of the haunted, despised house, 124, colored in gray and white on Bluestone Road. When Baby Sugg's freedom was paid by her son, Halle, the house 124 was given to her by the Bodwins in the free community of the Blacks in Cincinnati. This house became a center of

refuge and emotional-cultural gathering of the Black people because Baby Suggs had tendency to impart her community the lessons of love and companionship, but she stopped preaching and reduced her position to a bed-ridden patient just after Sethe's unexpected, violent act of infanticide. Even after her physical death, we feel her presence through the respectful memories, preserved by Sethe, Denver and the members of her community. The spiritual resurrection of Baby Suggs helps Denver and other black women in driving away the haunting soul of the Beloved from the despised house. Before the arrival of Paul D, both Sethe and her eighteen-year-old daughter, Denver were living in the house with the unseen presence of the ghost with whom they had tried to adjust themselves.

The present free situation of Sethe gets over-shadowed with the past, gruesome memories of slavery at Mr. Garner's Sweet Home Plantation in Kentucky. Even after the lapse of twenty years, all these memories got revived with the sympathetic presence of Paul D who had undergone also the brutality of slavery at the plantation. Morrison employs her narrative art of magical realism very carefully unfold the psychological dilemma of both Paul D, who is suffering from his devaluation of manhood or masculinity, and Sethe, who is haunted by the past guilt of infanticide. The story moves on two temporal planes—the first one includes the loving gestures between Paul D and Sethe, along with the spooky, ambiguous identity of Beloved which constitutes the present of the story at house, 124 in Cincinnati, and another the second one includes a series of unshared, unbearable events of past slavery, mostly taking place in Kentucky, around twenty years earlier, constitutes the buried past of the story. Through the fragmented flashbacks of the major characters, the writer reveals the psychological dilemma of the past slavery which may not be erased or cured easily.

Sethe recalls her teenage years when she was working with Sixo, Paul D, Paul F, Paul A and Halle at the plantation of Sweet Home, and ultimately she got herself married to Halle. Her problem began when the plantation was given to the charge of the sadist, racist schoolteacher and his nephews. Sethe had two sons and an infant baby when her pregnant body was violated by the nephews. She complained against them for they had stolen her milk, stored in her breast. Consequently, for her daring act of complaining, she had been whipped severely by the schoolteacher. The psychological impact of traumatic slavery and mute suffering has been carved into the shape of 'a chokecherry tree' on the back of Sethe, but it was sublimated with the sympathetic gestures of Amy Denver. Paul D, too, tries to regain his psychological normalcy by reflecting his masculinity before Sethe and Denver. Morrison has depicted the buried, degrading memories of Paul D as a 'tin tobacco box' which remains packed and closed tightly. After his horrible experiences at Sweet Home under the dictatorship of the School teacher and his survival as a member of the chain gang at Alfred in Georgia, he had been suffering from the psychological dilemma of identity-crisis. His insensitive, traumatic body had been evaluated in terms of money, very much like a tough iron machine which has nothing to complain against the inhumanity of the white master. The degrading experiences of Paul D had put him into a psychological condition of demoralized manhood because his sufferings were nothing before the traumatic enslaved body of Sethe, and naturally, he tried to restore his masculinity by comforting Sethe: "He would not try it loose now in from this sweet sturdy woman, for if she got a whiff on the contents it would shame him. And it would hurt her to know that there was no red heart bright as Mister's comb beating in him" (Morrison: 2005:86). Paul D realized for the first time the intense emotional injuries of Sethe during their separation of eighteen years, and now he tried to gain unspoken affection from Sethe for him. At the same time, he attempted to

redeem his manhood in the era of post-slavery by spending his last two dollars for the pleasure of Sethe and Denver.

In such a harmonious situation when both Paul D and Sethe were trying to redeem their past trauma and guilt, the mysterious figure of Beloved appeared at the house 124, increasing the number from three to four. Her wobbly, unstable head reminded Sethe of the partially severed head of an infant from its neck. Morrison adds the element of supernaturalism to the circular plot of her novel with the appearance of ghostlike Beloved and the disappearance of the dog, Here Boy, because it is a general belief that animals easily recognize the presence of evil or ghost. The ghostly presence of Beloved was felt earlier also which had frightened and driven Howard and Bugler, the two elder sons of Sethe, away the house, 124. Sethe also wished to leave the spiteful house, but she remained there at the hopeful suggestions of Baby Suggs. This time, with the physical presence of Beloved, Sethe felt optimistic by visualizing an emotional and caring bond between Denver and the spooky female figure. The mysterious activities and interior monologues constitute the climax of Morrison's magical realism, since she connects the natural world to that of supernatural, the traumas of the pre-slavery to their freedom of the post-slavery era and the personal history of inhuman slavery to the general history of the millions of enslaved people, perished and lost during the Trans Atlantic slave trade and their exploitation for the economic progress of the white.

Morrison's language is intensely poetic when she describes the presence and past merging into one in the allegorical figure of *Beloved*. The poetic language with color imagery and the symbols of Nature's objects release the suppressed feeling of motherhood and the love for the lost sibling on the part of Sethe and Denver. In chapter 23 of Part II in *Beloved*, we get the

mingling voices of Beloved, Denver and Sethe, overwhelming one another with their liberated voices.

“Beloved,

You are my sister.

You are my daughter.

You are my face; you are me.

I have found you again; you have come back to me.

You are my Beloved.

You are mine” (Morrison: 2005: 255).

Sethe was trapped by the ghostly presence of *Beloved* so much that she became entirely oblivious of the presence of Denver and Paul D. When Denver came out and sought help from the other black women, a group of thirty women exorcized the ghost of Beloved from the psychology of Sethe. The presence and character of *Beloved* in the life of Sethe at house, 124 may be appreciated as a skilful presentation of magical realism. The primary theme of this African-American novel is the lost motherhood and Sethe's unconscious yearning to fulfil the demands of motherhood. As an enslaved being, Sethe had been denied her right to feed the child with her breast milk; she killed her third child, in a bid to protect her from traumatic slavery, but her suppressed feelings of motherhood used to haunt her all the time. When she recalled the past traumatic experience of infanticide before Paul D, her psychological trauma of infanticide came in the form of twenty-year old female child as Beloved. During the process of exorcising, *Beloved* was spared and Edwin Bodwin, along with other slave-catchers were supposed to be killed. The support and solidarity of the black community of Cincinnati, Ohio, driving away the evil spirit from the house of 124, was an act of healing and regeneration of human culture with

Christian beliefs which was needed urgently to cure the psychological trauma of slavery from which most of the blacks continued to suffer even in post-slavery era. The ghost is supposed to return to her grave in peace, clamouring, no longer, for her mother's love.

Morrison calls the traumatic memories of slavery, from which Sethe had been suffering from the last twenty years, as "an unpleasant dream" (Morrison: 2005: 324), and naturally she concludes the novel, "This is not a story to pass on" (Morrison: 2005: 324), but she also confesses that she was overwhelmed to know "that my books haunt, that is what I work very hard for and for me; it is an achievement when they haunt readers" (quoted in Anderson: 2008: 47). Morrison's art of magical realism is vying with her theme of psychological realism because no slave narrative has, so far, revealed the psychological dilemma of slavery through the narrative technique of supernaturalism and reincarnation of the dead soul. Here we can compare the guilt of the Ancient Mariner with the hidden guilt of Sethe, the mother, because, as soon as they were reminded of their abnormal act of killing an innocent being, whether an Albatross or a child, they entered the realm of resurrection and supernaturalism to pacify their guilt-ridden, restless soul.

Morrison took six years to complete her fifth novel, *Beloved* in which she introduced the magic of African-American folklore, the mythical songs and other oral traditions of the Black Community to develop the theme of painful memory as a kind of emotional or psychological crisis to an enslaved mother like Sethe. In the words of Abdennebi, "As memory is but a moment of fear and trembling, a moment that shakes the body, and like an unexpected storm, shatters its wholeness, disturbs its restless quietness. It is at the difficult moment of training oneself to throw the past behind, that once awakened, hurled back to the past through the ever-persistent pain" (Abdennebi: 2010: 91). The psychological, imaginative picture of *Beloved* in Sethe's mind or

memory resembles her reincarnation or rebirth; her unadulterated, soft and gentle gestures take Sethe's mind back to twenty years when she had liked to feed her breast milk or when she had sacrificed her female body and its chastity for the engraving of Beloved's name on the tombstone of her killed Baby. Thus, Beloved is nothing but the reflection or embodiment of Sethe's the third killed child which has formed the overwhelming part of her past memories of slavery.

Morrison introduces the painful emotional bondage between Sethe and Beloved as the collective consciousness of all the Black enslaved mothers who got separated from their children through the slave trade in the middle passage, without recording or expressing their filial desires or dreams. Even though the novel is divided into three parts, accommodating twenty-eight chapters, yet these chapters go without any date and number that indicate their timeless nature, covering all the enslaved generations or groups belonging to their regions of slavery. Morrison has employed both the oral and written discourses through the repetition of words, phrases and passages. The chapters in Part I of the novel generally open with the morbid nature of the house, 124 which is the center of the action. The house is a concrete reality, but it does also form a psychological reality of missing third child of Sethe since the house bears the number, 124, omitting no. 3 that is the number of the third child, Beloved. The very basis of psychological realism remains rooted in the feminine crisis, whether the white or the black ____ starving motherhood, longing sisterhood, female kinship during the moments of crisis and healing up the psychological scars through love and companionship. The repetition of the short sentences, words and phrases emphasize the unchanging position of the psychological reality. The surviving Black characters, like Sethe, Paul D, Stamp Paid and Denver always recall Baby Suggs and her preachings, because Morrison wants to show the emotional obligation between the past and the present in the Black community since they feel the presence of their dead ancestors as their

guiding spirit. Morrison also tries to correct the myth of slavery, regarding the kind treatment of the white-slave owners. Baby Suggs experienced her status of a slave both in the administration of Mr. Garner and the Bodwins, but whatever might be their treatment to her, she felt herself all the time under the obligation of a slave.

Morrison wants to say that the lack of proper and effective communication in the slave community also produced the chaotic and disastrous consequences. When Sethe along, with her three children, had taken refuge at Baby Suggs' house, the approaching movement of the slave-catchers was not informed to either Sethe or Baby Suggs by any black person. Sethe felt herself humiliated so much by her isolated condition that she didn't ask for any help from her black community even after her release from jail. *Beloved*, as a symbol of the buried past memories, stands for the chaos and disunity of human sensitivity, and this fact have been highlighted by the disjointed sentences, omitted important words and expressions. The disconnected, incoherent statements lead us to discover the abnormal condition of events that start taking place at 124 just after the appearance of *Beloved*. Morrison's task behind writing this novel is to transform the memories of the past into a historical discourse, and it is for this reason that we get the frequency of flashbacks either through conversation or through reflections and thoughts. Morrison uses the trope of memory to revise the genre of slave narratives and thereby, makes the slave experience or the psychological realities of slave life accessible to the contemporary readers. We get a number of passages in the novel which maintain the narrative balance between remembering and forgetting.

The language of the psychological novel depicts the interior landscape of the characters, and naturally, the linguistic design moves with certain invoking images and symbols. This kind of symbolic language is generally appreciated as 'the impressionistic painting'. In this novel

also, Morrison includes a number of images and symbols, but the important among them are the color red, the form of trees, the tin Tobacco Box and the hopping Rooster, Mister. The African slaves were employed in the rural areas with far-stretched plantations of cotton and tobacco, and naturally, they were transported through water. That's way, they tried to escape through the wild hilly areas and narrow tunnels. The novel presents a good deal of pastoral descriptions with natural wild plants and animals, birds and insects of the rural areas. The scars of whipping on the back of Sethe look like a stunted tree, without any growth, signifying her emotional and spiritual death. Nevertheless, it was Amy Denver who anticipated the blossoming branches of the tree, which might indicate the reviving emotional life of the traumatic slave girl. Denver, too, gets a feeling of solace in her emerald closet, full of boxwood bushes. When Paul D starts running to the unknown path of freedom, he tries to follow neither the Whiteman's path nor the Blackman's path, but to the path of flowering trees to the North.

The other functional image or symbol is Paul D's the tin Tobacco Box which stands for his suppressed and mute heart. While serving the brutish schoolteacher at the plantation of Sweet Home, Paul D's hands are chained behind his back and his tongue is held down by an iron bit. His degrading, inhuman condition forced him not to think and feel like a human being, and he decided never to open his horrible past of slavery before any woman, but his dead, dried heart got revived with the affectionate words and gestures of both Sethe and Beloved. At the same time, Paul D also felt his masculinity challenged by the movement of the Rooster, named Mister. Mister had the privilege to maintain its real identity by flapping amidst the hens and by sitting on the tub. Pual D felt envious of the rooster, Mister since it had not been victimized by the racial aggression till its death or killing, but the identity or the birth of Paul D had been reduced to a beast of burden by the aggressive forces of racism. That's why, Paul D lamented that he would

never be a proud, normal man, and that his human psychology or sensitivity had been so much devastated by the schoolteacher that he felt himself “less than a chicken sitting in the sun on a tub” (Morrison: 2005: 86).

Morrison offers various color imageries in this novel- blue, green, lavender, pink and red which have their magical effect on the lives of the traumatized people. Baby Suggs tries to relish the last dregs of her free life by enjoying colors, around her death bed. Paul D’s heart was still red in his tightly sealed tin Tobacco Box which indicates that despite the brutality of slavery, his heart still longed for human companionship and sensation. Amy Denver has red velvet with her which gives the message of hope for colorful future of Sethe at Ohio. When Paul D arrived at the house 124, he went out, along with Sethe and Denver, to enjoy the thrilling carnival of the Black people for the first time, and all three of them noticed the fencing of the red roses on their way to lumberyard; at the same time, they also smelt the dying scent of the withering roses. The blooming and withering of the red roses symbolize the flickering hope of peaceful, harmonious life to Denver, Sethe and Paul D through their bond. The word ‘red’ recurs throughout the novel, and it signifies the various contexts of violence, sex, energy and vitality as per the structure of text. The twenty-eight chapters of this novel also constitute the menstrual cycle of 28 days after which a female body gets ready to conceive and to fulfil the longings of being a mother. Following the feminism and ethnicity of Zora Neale Hurston, Gwendlyn Brooks and Paule Marshall, Morrison rebuilds the damaged psychology of the Black female characters by curing them of their shameful past and also by inculcating a confidence in them to accept their past as their historical-cultural legacy.

Conclusion:

Morrison has employed the element of supernaturalism and reincarnation in her novel *Beloved* to expose the traumatic burden of guilt, suppressed longings of a mother and the miseries of inhuman slavery from which Sethe, the helpless mother and Paul D, the last fugitive survivor of the Sweet Home plantation suffered intensely. This psychological problem of existential dilemma and identity crisis is directly related to the inner man or the emotional man which can be expressed only through the narrative technique of magic realism. Morrison's magic realism is as much complex as the riddled psychology of Sethe and Paul D, but through their reflections, interior monologues and frequent mixing of the past with the present, it becomes highly convincing and effective. *Beloved* becomes a timeless historical record of the Trans-Atlantic slave trade and its lasting effect on the succeeding generation of the African-Americans, because like Baby Suggs, Sethe and Paul D, the free generation of the black people feel themselves burdened with their past memories of slavery. In *Beloved*, Morrison has given the Biblical references to attain salvation and to get rid of the past sins through sacrifice, redemption, forgiveness, love and resurrection. The epigraph of the novel itself is a master piece of magical realism because it connects the humanity of the white people with the degrading condition of the Blacks through the Christian gospels. Through the psychological resurrection of the killed baby, *Beloved* helps in resurrecting or restoring the healthy, normal human mind to both Sethe and Paul D. It is rightly said that the mythic African structure and Morrison's magical realism provide "a spiritual and cultural bridge between the history of the character's ancestors and the lives of the characters" living in the present (Beaulieu: 2003: 79).

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